

Cardiac Risk Assessment in Covid-19 Vaccine Recipients: An Observational Analysis

Thenmozhi.P¹, Joseph Raja Y², Dr.Tamilselvi.S³, Dr.Bhuvaneswari.G³, Dr.Mary Minolin.T³

^{1,3}Professor, Saveetha College of Nursing, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India

²Saveetha College of Nursing, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India

E-Mail id: thenmozhi.sethu@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Background: Cardiovascular diseases remain a major global health concern, accounting for nearly one-third of all deaths worldwide. Although COVID-19 vaccination reduces infection-related cardiac complications, concerns persist regarding post-vaccination cardiac risk, prompting this study to assess cardiac risk levels among COVID-19 vaccinated individuals. **Methods:** An observational study was conducted to assess cardiac risk among 100 Covid 19 vaccinated individuals aged 30–50 years at the outpatient department of Saveetha Medical College and Hospital. Participants who received either Covishield or Covaxin were selected using purposive sampling. Demographic and clinical data were collected via a structured questionnaire, and cardiac risk was assessed using the Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease (ASCVD) risk score. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics in SPSS, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant. **Results:** Among the participants, 47% had intermediate cardiac risk, 23% low risk, 22% borderline risk, and 8% high risk. Regression analysis revealed no significant association between demographic or lifestyle variables and cardiac risk, though the model explained 17.7% of the variance in risk scores. **Conclusion:** A considerable proportion of vaccinated individuals exhibited intermediate cardiac risk, while few had high risk. Demographic and lifestyle factors showed limited influence on cardiac risk, suggesting that other physiological factors may contribute. Continued monitoring and further research are recommended to better understand post-vaccination cardiac outcomes.

Keywords: ASCVD risk score; cardiac risk; cardiovascular diseases; COVID -19;

COVID-19 vaccination

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) continue to pose a major global health challenge, contributing substantially to morbidity and mortality worldwide. According to the NHS, there are four main types of CVDs: coronary heart disease (e.g., angina, heart attacks, and heart failure), stroke and transient ischemic attacks (TIAs), peripheral arterial disease, and aortic diseases¹. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that approximately 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2019, accounting for 32% of all global deaths, with 85% of these deaths attributed to heart attacks and strokes. More than three-quarters of CVD-related deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries². By 2030, the annual number of deaths from CVDs is projected to exceed 22.2 million^{3,4}. Evidence from national and international studies indicates an increasing prevalence of CVD-related mortality, contributing to rising healthcare costs⁵⁻⁷. Understanding the diverse risk factors associated with CVDs is essential for developing effective prevention and management strategies. In addition to preventing severe SARS-CoV-2 infection, COVID-19 vaccination has been shown to reduce the risk of cardiovascular complications associated with the infection itself. However, COVID-19 vaccines, particularly messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) vaccines have also been linked to cardiac complications such as myocarditis and pericarditis, albeit at a much lower rate than those occurring after COVID-19 infection. The SARS-CoV-2 virus, the seventh known coronavirus capable of infecting humans⁸, has caused more than 6.7 million deaths and over 660 million confirmed cases globally to date⁹. Cardiovascular risk factors, advanced age, and preexisting comorbidities have been identified as predictors of worse clinical outcomes, including higher rates

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of intensive care unit admission and mortality¹⁰. Studies have indicated that mRNA vaccines are associated with an elevated risk of myocarditis^{11,12}; however, there is little evidence suggesting a higher incidence of these events following the second dose¹³. Conversely, mRNA vaccines have also demonstrated a protective effect against myocardial infarction¹⁴. Numerous observational studies have reported that individuals with SARS-CoV-2 infection experience myocardial and cardiac dysfunction, along with cardiovascular complications such as myocarditis, pericarditis, arrhythmias, acute myocardial infarction, stroke, thromboembolism, and sudden cardiac death^{15,16}. Autopsy studies have further elucidated the cardiac pathology associated with SARS-CoV-2, revealing viral presence within the myocardium—not only in cardiomyocytes but also in interstitial cells, pericytes, and macrophages¹⁷. Despite these findings, there remains a gap in understanding whether the reduction in serious cardiac events following COVID-19 vaccination is also associated with a decline in post-COVID cardiovascular impairment or persistent symptoms. This gap highlights the need for further research to explore the prevalence of cardiac risks among individuals who have received the COVID-19 vaccine. Hence, the present study was undertaken to assess the prevalence of cardiac risks among COVID-19–vaccinated individuals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A quantitative approach with a non-experimental observational research design was adopted to assess cardiac risk among COVID-19 vaccinated individuals in the outpatient department of Saveetha Medical College and Hospital after obtaining formal permission. Hundred COVID-19 vaccinated individuals who met the inclusion criteria were selected using a purposive sampling technique. The inclusion criteria for the study were males and females aged between 30 and 50 years who had received either the Covishield or Covaxin vaccine and were willing to participate in the study. The investigator introduced herself and provided a brief introduction about the purpose of the study. Participants were seated comfortably in a well-ventilated room, and confidentiality regarding their data was assured to gain their cooperation during data collection. Informed verbal and written consent were obtained from participants regarding their willingness to participate in the study. Demographic and clinical characteristics were collected using a structured questionnaire designed by the investigator through an interview method. Following this, the prevalence of cardiac risk was assessed using the Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease (ASCVD) risk score assessment tool. The tool included factors such as age, sex, race, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, comorbidities, smoking status,

blood pressure treatment with medication, aspirin therapy, and current risk estimation based on previous visit data. The total score was interpreted as follows: <5% - low risk, 5% to 7.5% - Borderline risk, 7.5% to 20% - intermediate risk, and >20% - high risk. Each participant took approximately 25 to 30 minutes to complete the data collection. All ethical principles were adhered to throughout the research study.

Statistics:

The collected data were organized and entered into MS Excel for further analysis and interpretation using descriptive and inferential statistics based on the study objectives with the SPSS statistical package. Background variables and level of cardiac risk were presented in terms of percentage, means, and standard deviations. A p-value of 0.05 or less was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1. Background Variables of the Participants

Background Variables	Study Group
Age (in Years)	41 ± 3.22
Gender (Male/Female)	60% / 40%
Education (High School / Higher Secondary / UG / PG)	5% / 63% / 22% / 10%
Occupation (Coolie / IT Professional / Govt employee / Business)	23% / 6% / 48% / 23%
Residence (Rural / Urban)	33% / 67%
Habits (Smoking / Alcoholism / Both / None)	12% / 8% / 13% / 67%
Body Mass Index	38.27 ± 3.84
Dietary Habits (Vegetarian / Non-vegetarian)	15% / 85%
Co-morbidities (DM / HT / Both / None)	15% / 50% / 10% / 25%
Affected by COVID 19 (Yes / No)	20% / 80%
Vaccinated with (Covishield / COVAXin)	62% / 38%

Table 1 presents the sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the 60 COVID-19–vaccinated participants. the mean age was 41 ± 3.22 years. The majority (60%) were male, and 63% had completed higher secondary education. Nearly 48% were employed in the government sector, and 67% resided in urban areas. About 13% reported both smoking and alcohol consumption as habits. The mean BMI score was 38.27 ±

3.84. Half of the participants (50%) had hypertension as a comorbid condition. In addition, 80% had not been previously affected by COVID-19, and 62% had received the Covishield vaccine.

As illustrated in Figure 1, nearly half of the participants (47%) had an intermediate cardiac risk, followed by 23% with low risk, 22% with borderline risk, and 8% with high cardiac risk.

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of Cardiac Risk Scores

Level of Cardiac Risk	Mean ± SD
Low risk (<5%)	3.21 ± 1.21
Borderline risk (5% to 7.5%)	4.62 ± 2.13
Intermediate risk (7.5% to 20%)	6.12 ± 1.76
High risk (>20%)	6.98 ± 2.43
Overall Score	8.80 ± 4.98

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation of cardiac risk scores among the study participants. The results show that individuals with high cardiac risk (>20%) had the highest mean score (6.98 ± 2.43), followed by those with intermediate risk (7.5%–20%) with a mean score of 6.12 ± 1.76. Participants classified as having borderline risk (5%–7.5%) had a mean score of 4.62 ± 2.13, while those with low risk (<5%) had the lowest mean score (3.21 ± 1.21). The overall mean cardiac risk score was 8.80 ± 4.98, indicating a predominance of participants in the intermediate to high-risk categories.

Table 3. Multiple Regression Analysis to assess the influencing factors of cardiac risk

Influencing Factors	Unstandardized	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval
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	Coefficients		Beta	t	g.	val for B	
	B	Standard Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Age	.626	.852	.123	.735	.466	-1.090	2.342
Sex	-2.201	1.757	-.218	-1.253	.217	-5.740	1.337
Education	1.194	1.118	.176	1.068	.291	-1.057	3.444
Occupation	.327	1.053	.071	.311	.757	-1.795	2.449
Residence	-.115	1.029	-.018	-.112	.911	-2.187	1.957
Comorbidities	.056	.751	.012	.074	.941	-1.456	1.568
Habits	.355	.842	.075	.421	.676	-1.342	2.051
Dietary Pattern	.961	1.078	.144	.891	.378	-1.211	3.132
BMI	-.794	1.131	-.109	-.702	.486	-3.072	1.484
Affected by Covid-19	-.154	1.820	-.012	-.085	.933	-3.820	3.511
Vaccinated against Covid-19	2.650	1.570	.261	1.688	.098	-.511	5.811
R² Change – 17.7%							

Table 3 presents the results of multiple linear regression analysis performed to identify the influencing factors of cardiac risk among individuals vaccinated against COVID-19. The analysis showed that none of the independent variables such as age, sex, education, occupation, residence, comorbidities, habits, dietary pattern, BMI, prior COVID-19 infection, and vaccination status had a statistically significant relationship with cardiac risk (p > 0.05). The R² change value of 17.7% indicates that the demographic and health-related variables collectively explain 17.7% of the variance in cardiac risk among COVID-19–vaccinated individuals. This suggests that other unexamined factors may contribute to the remaining unexplained variance in cardiac risk.

DISCUSSION

COVID-19 and its common comorbidities share key inflammatory and cytokine-related molecular pathways centered on CCL2, IL6, IL10, and TLR4, indicating common genetic mechanisms that may underlie disease severity and providing insights for targeted therapeutic strategies¹⁸. Clinical trials conducted in the early phases reported that mRNA vaccines conferred around 95% efficacy against SARS-CoV-2 infection¹⁹. Even with waning effectiveness over time, recent CDC reports indicate that COVID-19 vaccines still confer significant protection against key clinical outcomes, including hospitalization, critical illness, and death²⁰. Kleebayoon A et al. stated that the trend of breakthrough SARS-CoV-2 infections was lower among immunocompromised patients receiving pre-exposure prophylactic monoclonal antibodies who had received all doses of the COVID-19 vaccine, emphasizing the continued importance of complete vaccination in this high-risk group²¹. The occurrence of myocarditis following Comirnaty vaccination is recognized and reported in its prescribing information (USPI) within the Warnings and Precautions and Adverse Reactions sections²². Multiple large pharmaco-epidemiological studies from the United States, France, Nordic countries, and the United Kingdom, along with a meta-analysis, indicate that myocarditis following COVID-19 vaccination is extremely rare²³⁻²⁷. However, the greatest risk of myocarditis has been observed in young males within 14 days following the second dose of the primary mRNA COVID-19 vaccination series²⁸. Additionally, data from the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) using the Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System (VAERS) show that myocarditis occurs less frequently following a booster dose than after the second dose of the primary vaccination series²⁹. Several studies have compared myocarditis risk following COVID-19 infection and vaccination. Evidence from a systematic review and meta-analysis indicates that the risk of developing myocarditis after COVID-19 infection is approximately 42 times higher than after vaccination³⁰, highlighting the overall protective benefit of vaccination. The current study assessed cardiac risk levels among COVID-19–vaccinated individuals and explored the association of demographic, health-related, and lifestyle factors with cardiac risk scores. The findings showed that a large proportion of participants exhibited intermediate cardiac risk, while smaller proportions fell into low, borderline, or high-risk categories. None of the independent variables examined (age, sex, education, occupation, comorbidities, or lifestyle habits) were significantly associated with cardiac risk, and the regression model explained 17.7% of the variance in cardiac risk scores. Yiyi XU et al reported that risk of myopericarditis, extrasystoles, and transient ischaemic attack was transiently increased after COVID-19 vaccination, but full vaccination substantially reduced the risk of several more severe COVID-19-associated cardiovascular outcomes, underscoring the protective benefits of complete vaccination³¹. Similarly, Jain Supriya et al. emphasized that although

patients with COVID-19 vaccine–associated myocarditis often experience a mild initial illness and favorable mid-term outcomes, the presence of myocardial injury at onset and its persistence over time underscore the need for continued monitoring and long-term follow-up studies³². Notably, Yun C et al observed that younger recipients of mRNA vaccines exhibited a higher risk of heart disease compared with older individuals, suggesting that further research is required to understand the underlying mechanisms and optimize vaccination strategies³³. A study by Daungsupawong H et al found a possible relationship between COVID-19 vaccination or infection and the occurrence of coronary artery disease (CAD) in Turkish patients; however, the findings should be interpreted with caution because of limitations in the study design and statistical analysis³⁴. Overall, both the literature and the current study indicate that serious cardiac complications following COVID-19 vaccination are uncommon. Limitations of this study include the absence of electrocardiogram, echocardiography, and cardiac enzyme assessments, which could better detect subclinical or early cardiac effects.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the present study indicate that a considerable proportion of COVID-19 vaccinated individuals exhibited the cardiac risk. Although demographic factors did not show a statistically significant association with cardiac risk, the regression model explained 17.7% of the variance in cardiac risk scores. These results suggest that while vaccination status and basic demographic variables have limited influence, other physiological or behavioral factors may contribute to post-vaccination cardiac risk and warrant further investigation.

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